

Gender and Locus of Control as Predictors of Career Decision-Making among Students of Public Secondary Schools in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

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Abstract

The study investigated gender and locus of control as predictors of career decision-making among students of public secondary schools in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. Descriptive survey design was employed for the study. A population of four thousand five hundred (4,500) SS11 students were target respondents. The population consisted of 2,366 males and 2,134 females. A sample of four hundred and fifty (450) was drawn consisting of 237 males and 213 females using 10% of the population. To enable every member of the population to have a known and equal chance of being selected from the sample, 10 selected public secondary schools were selected from the 34 secondary schools in Yenagoa, using stratified random sampling techniques. A self-developed 'Gender and Locus of Control Career Decision-Making Questionnaire' (GLCCDMQ) was used to collect the data. The index of the instrument was $r = 0.75$ for decision-making, 0.84 for locus of control and 0.85 for the entire instrument. Three research questions were raised and three hypotheses were tested for the study. Data were analyzed using simple percentage, mean and standard deviation for demographic variables and research questions, while multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The study found that gender significantly predict the career decision-making of the male students than their female counterparts. It was also found that students' locus of control predicts their career decision-making in school with those with external locus of control being more predictive than the internal students. A significant joint prediction of gender and locus of control on career decision-making among students of public secondary schools was established with locus of control being more significant than gender. It was concluded that career decision-making challenges will be affected by the way students view gender in relationship to career choice, as well as their perception of locus of control either as external or internal. It was recommended that school counsellors should consider gender and locus of control as variables that may influence career decision-making of students' during their counselling sessions, so they can help the students make informed and realistic career decisions.

Keywords: Gender, locus of control, career and decision-making

Introduction

Arranging males and females into social roles creates an issue, since people feel that they should belong to one side of a direct range and should recognize themselves as man or lady, as opposed to being permitted to pick a part in the middle. Young men and young ladies go through various mingling encounters and will, in general, learn diverse sex roles and standards of conduct and foster various interests. Gender keeps on essentially affecting the career paths of senior secondary school students on account of the well-established generalizations about people. Putting stock in the mediocrity of women compared to men is so great that the career differential is frequently seen influencing everything during the course selection process in school (Kayode, Olusegun & Olukemi, 2016). These jobs and interests later become predominant components of the career dynamic.

Gender, as defined by Adigun, Onihunwa, Irunokhai, Sadi, and Adesina (2015), is a set of physical, mental, and behavioural characteristics relating to and distinguishing between manly and ladylike (male and female) populations. Gender is socially developed, for the most part, from customarily held convictions and mentalities, since gender personality is learnt, not set up upon entering the world. Hence, it ought not to be viewed as a measuring stick in picking and seeking after an ideal career.

Individuals' convictions about specific circumstances limit their ability to have smart demeanors, thereby narrowing their possibilities, desires, and eventually agreeing to less. Henceforth, you might think that it is helpful to foster your dynamic and critical thinking abilities, which can empower one to take a more noteworthy responsibility for things instead of accusing conditions or powers outside ones' ability to control when things turn out badly. The locus of control alludes to a singular's certainty about the hidden fundamental driver of events in his/her life. It is a singular's conviction in regards to the reasons for their encounters and the components to which that individual credits achievement or disappointment (Zagi, Ayu & Daniel, 2018). Locus of control can impact not just how one reacts to the events that occur in a man's life, but additionally, ones' inspiration to make a move (Kendra, 2019). This infers that in the event that one accepts that one holds the keys to one destiny, one is bound to make a move to change one's circumstances when required. In the event that, then again, one accepts that the result is out of one hands, man might be more averse to pursuing change.

Career improvement is a cycle that prompts a choice. Picking a career is a perplexing choice that ought not to be made in a rush because the only way to guarantee work fulfilment is to settle on a comprehensive and practical career choice. Austin (2010) noted that without career direction, secondary school students are generally unreliable concerning career choice. As a result, in terms of career, expanding attention entails shifting the individual's assumptions following the truth that confronts the students. As indicated by Siriwan (2011), "career dynamic" is "a cycle that portrays or clarifies the decisions that an individual makes while choosing a specific career". The decision of subject and subject blends at the senior secondary school level isn't made discretionarily.

A few students cannot settle on a decision without the assistance of career officials or guides who need to guarantee that the blend of the subjects picked should prompt a course of study the individual has as a primary concern to seek after at college or other tertiary foundations. The focal point of this review is to research if gender and locus of control are predictors of career dynamics among senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa.

Statement of the Problem

The expanding pace of joblessness settles on the formative undertaking of career dynamic lumbering as students are more inspired by careers that can ensure business independence of their essential spaces of interest and possibilities; the resultant impact is career maladjustment. If young people are not very much directed, heaps of misled choices might be made because of restricted or no solid data to direct their career decisions, with the subsequent consequence of settling on rushed and unreasonable career choices that seem at first encouraging yet become unsuitable throughout their scholastic interest.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to examine gender and locus of control as predictors of career decision-making among students of public secondary schools in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. The study specifically is expected to achieve the following objectives.

1. Determine the extent to which gender predicts career decision-making of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.
2. Determine the extent to which locus of control predicts career decision-making of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.
3. Determine the extent to which gender and locus of control jointly predicts career decision-making of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. To what extent does gender predict career decision-making of senior secondary School students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State?
2. To what extent does locus of control predict career decision-making of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State?
3. To what extent does gender and locus of control jointly predict career decision-making of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the career decision making of male and female secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

2. There is no significant difference between internal and external locus of control of senior secondary school students in career decision-making in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.
3. There is no significant joint prediction of gender and locus of control on career decision-making of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted for this study which was designed to investigate gender and locus of control as predictors of career decision-making among senior secondary school students' in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. The population consisted of all the senior secondary school students of SS11. A sample of four hundred and fifty (450) students consisting of 237 males and 213 females drawn from 10% of the population were selected for the study. To enable every member of the population to have a known and equal chance of being selected from the sample, 10 public secondary schools were selected from the 34 secondary schools in Yenagoa, using stratified random sampling techniques.

Gender and locus of control as predictors of career decision-making questionnaire (GLCPCDMQ) was used for the study. It is a 26-items questionnaire divided into three sections of demographic variables, locus of control and career decision-making, developed by the researchers to measure the extent to which students believe that they can control the events that affect them, as well as the students' thinking process regarding their educational and career plans, structured on a four point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD).

The instrument was subjected to face and content validities by an expert in the Department of Educational Foundations, Niger Delta University. He endorsed the instrument as having content and face validities. The instrument was trial tested using test-re-test procedure that yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.75 for decision-making, 0.75; locus of control, 0.84 and the entire instrument, 0.85. The reliability coefficient values were noted to be an acceptable reliability values that can promote the use of the instrument for data collection in the study.

A total of 450 questionnaires were administered out of which 449 were retrieved. The simple percentage analyses of the demographic data revealed that 234 (52 percent) of the respondents were male, on the other hand, 215 (48 percent) were female. Similarly, 56 (12 percent) of the respondents had external locus of control and 393 (88 percent) had internal locus of control. Multiple regression analysis was used to examine the joint and relative prediction of the independent variables (Gender and Locus of Control) on the dependent variable career decision-making.

Results

Analysis of Demographic Data

Data were analyzed using simple percentage, mean, and standard deviation for demographic variables and research questions.

Table 1: Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Gender

S/N	Gender	Frequencies	Percentage (%)
1	Male	234	52
2	Female	215	48
3	Total	449	100

The data presented in Table 1 indicated that 234 (52 percent) of the respondents were male, on the other hand, 215 (48 percent) were female. This simply implies that male respondents were more in number than their female counterparts in the study.

Table 2: Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Locus of Control

S/N	Locus of Control	Frequencies	Percentage (%)
1	External	56	12
2	Internal	393	88
3	Total	449	100

The data presented in Table 2 showed that, 56 (12 percent) had external and 393 (88 percent) had internal locus of control. This implies that respondents with internal locus of control were more than their counterparts' with external locus of control.

Research Question One

To what extent does gender predict career decision-making of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State?

Table 3: Summary of mean and standard deviation scores of the extent gender predicts students' career decision-making in schools

Gender	N	X	SD
Male	234	42.590	3.555
Female	215	32.820	5.393
Total	449	37.910	6.661

The data presented in Table 3 indicated that, the mean score of male students' (42.590) is greater than the mean score of female students' (32.82) on their career decision-making in schools. This implies that, gender has a composite contribution to the prediction of career decision-making among the male students than the female students. Hence, there is a difference between male and female students' in career decision-making. The male gender contributed more than the female gender. Consequent upon the observed difference, the Z-test analysis was carried out in order to ascertain if the difference is significant or not (see Table 4).

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between male and female students' career decision-making in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

Table 4: Z-test analysis of the difference between male and female students' career decision-making in schools

Gender	N	X	SD	Df	Z-cal.	Z-crit.	Sig.	Decision at P < 0.05
Male	234	42.590	3.555	447	22.848	1.960	0.000	*
Female	215	32.820	5.393					

* = Significant at 0.05 alpha level; N = 449

The data presented in Table 4 indicated that, the Z-test analysis is significant at 0.05 alpha level because the calculated Z-test value of 22.848 is greater than the critical table Z-test value of 1.960 at 0.05 alpha level with 447 degrees of freedom. Hence, the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant difference between male and female students' career decision-making in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State is rejected. This means that male gender differs significantly from their female counterparts in career decision making. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis which stated that, there is a significant difference between male and female senior secondary school students in career decision making in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State is upheld.

Research Question Two

To what extent does locus of control predict career decision-making of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

Table 5: Summary of mean and standard deviation scores of the difference between students with internal and external locus of control on their career decision making in schools.

Locus of Control	N	X	SD
External	56	41.910	5.096
Internal	393	37.340	6.667
Total	449	37.910	6.661

The data presented in Table 5 revealed that, the mean score of students with external locus of control (41.910) is greater than the mean score of those with internal locus of control (37.340) on their career decision-making in schools. This implies that, there existed a difference between students with external and internal locus of control on their career decision making in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State with those with external locus of control being more predictive than those with internal locus of control. Consequent upon the observed difference, the Z-test analysis was carried out in order to confirm if the difference is significant or not (see Table 6.).

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between students with external and internal locus of control on their career decision making in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

Table 6: Z-test analysis of the difference between male and female students with external and internal locus of control on their career decision making in schools

Locus of control	N	X	SD	Df	Z-cal.	Z-crit.	Sig.	Decision at P < 0.05
External	56	41.910	5.096	447	4.924	1.960	0.000	*
Internal	393	37.340	6.667					

*= Significant at 0.05 alpha level; N = 449

The data presented in Table 6 showed that, the Z-test analysis is significant at 0.05 alpha level because the calculated Z-test value of 4.924 is greater than the critical table Z-test value of 1.960 at 0.05 alpha level with 447 degrees of freedom. Hence, the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant difference between students with external and internal locus of control on their career decision making in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State was rejected. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis which stated that, there is a significant difference between students with external and internal locus of control on their career decision making in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State is upheld with those with external locus of control being more significant than the internal locus of control.

Research Question Three

To what extent does gender and locus of control jointly predicts career decision-making of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State?

Table 7: Multiple regression analysis of the joint prediction of gender and locus of control on career decision-making in schools

S/N	Variables	N	R	R ²
1	Gender*locus of control*Career decision-making	449	0.742	0.551

The data presented in Table 7 revealed a multiple regression index (R) of 0.742 with a multiple regression index square (R²) of 0.551. This showed that 55.100 percent of the total variance of students' career decision-making can be attributed to the joint prediction of gender and locus of control. In order to confirm whether this prediction is significant or not, the multiple regression analysis was further subjected to the F-test statistical analysis (See Table 8).

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant joint prediction of gender and locus of control on career decision-making of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

Table 8: F-statistics of multiple regression analysis of the joint prediction of gender and locus of control on career decision-making of senior secondary school students

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F.cal.	F.crit.	Sig.	Decision at P < 0.05
Regression	10953.085	2	5476.543		3.02	0.000	*
Residual	8922.527	446	20.006	273.750			
Total	19875.612	448					

* = *Significant at 0.05 alpha Level; N = 449.*

The data presented in Table 8 showed that, the F-statistics of multiple regression analysis is significant at $p < 0.05$ alpha level because, the calculated F- value of 273.750 is greater than the critical table F-value of 3.02 at 0.05 alpha level with 2 and 446 degrees of freedom. Hence, the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant joint prediction of gender and locus of control on career decision-making of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State is rejected. The alternative hypothesis which stated that, there is a significant joint prediction of gender and locus of control on career decision-making of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State is upheld. This means that gender and locus of control jointly and significantly predict career decision-making of senior secondary school students of Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. with locus of control being more significant than gender.

Discussion

The point of the review was to examine gender and locus of control as predictors of career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. The findings are organized and discussed according to the research questions and hypotheses postulated to guide the study. The consequence of the investigation of information showed a huge distinction between the male and female students on their career decision-making, with gender being more altogether prescient of the male students than the females. This suggested that students gender added to their career decision-making in schools. This is in concurrence with Eyo and Edet (2011), who found that there was a critical contrast among male and female students' career dynamics in schools. Watson, Creed, John, and Patton (2012) also revealed that gender impact on the developmental progression of career decisions. This review conflicts with Obiunu (2012), who found that sex was not a critical reality and had no impact on the decision-making course of a young adult.

The outcome additionally uncovered a difference between students with external and internal locus of control over their career decision making in senior secondary schools of Yenagoa, Bayelsa State with students with external locus of control being more predictive than those with internal locus of control. This implies that students' locus of control predicts their career decision-making in schools. The finding is in concurrence with Izuchi and Onomakpome (2018), who likewise found that locus of control predicts secondary school students' career choice decisions.

Similarly, it was also revealed that, there is a significant difference between students with external and internal locus of control on their career decision making in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State with those with external locus of control being more significant than

the internal locus of control. This finding corroborates with the study of Akpochafo (2017), who found a significant relationship between external locus of control and career decision-making of secondary school students.

The discoveries also showed that 55.100 percent of the total variance of students' career decision-making can be attributed to the joint prediction of gender and locus of control. This infer that gender and locus of control together add to students' career decision-making. This review conflicts with Obiunu (2012), who found that sex was not a critical reality and had no impact on the decision-making course of a young adult.

The study also revealed a significant joint prediction of gender and locus of control on career decision-making of senior secondary school students. This infer that gender and locus of control jointly and significantly predicts career decision-making of senior secondary school students of Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. This finding is steady with those of Turker and Inel (2012), who tracked down that the identification of students' locus of control and sex are important factors to consider in career decision-making of secondary school students.

Conclusion

The study concluded that gender predicts the career decision-making of senior secondary school students with a significant difference between the male and female students, that there is a significant difference between students with external and internal locus of control on their career decision-making, with those with external locus of control being more predictive than those with internal locus of control. Similarly, it was revealed that gender and locus of control significantly and jointly predicts career decision-making of students of senior secondary schools. This investigation shows that career decision-making challenges will be affected by the way students view gender in relationship to career choice, as well as their perception of locus of control either as external or internal.

Recommendations

1. Students should be encouraged to make realistic occupational choices that are in consonance with their personal characteristics and abilities, irrespective of their gender as his will make them fulfilling and satisfactory.
2. Since external locus of control was significant, counsellors should be guided by the external factors that influence students career decision-making by ensuring techniques that allows students to make career decisions based on their personal interests and decisions.
3. It could be necessary for working guidance counsellors in the field to consider gender and locus of control as variables that may influence career decision-making process of students, during their counselling sessions, so they can help the students make informed and realistic career decisions.

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